

THE LIMITS TO ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: DO MACHINES HAVE ETHICAL BIAS?

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POLICY STATEMENT

The artificial intelligence (AI) left science fiction movies to become part of the reality, present in our daily routine. We increasingly use services controlled by this technology, which start to interact more strongly with our lives. The utilization of AI-equipped tools and softwares compel society to reflect not only about the pertinence of its use, but above all on the ethical limits that must be respected so that the fundamental rights are preserved.

The utilization of AI as a mean to facial identification to give access to services or even to locate fugitives from justice, as well as the use of autonomous cars and weapons, controlled by smart softwares, demands an open and straight debate about what we will (and should) allow such equipment to do, not only replacing the humans in action diagnosis, but effectively taking decisions and acting as protagonists of social reality. It's not possible that we can dispense the use of such technological means.

Thus, more than ever, the social and scientific debate must be oriented towards imposing limits and reservations, not only to the development of these means. It is needed to question: are we willing to give up our intimacy and privacy in order to have a more technologically active life? In this sense, the dialogue between researchers and thinkers from different states about the subject is more and more necessary each day. Because despite the natural differences between the countries and their respective societies, the challenges are common and tend to demand shared solutions.

BACKGROUND

The development of new technologies always imposes new reflections to society, forcing to define not only juridical regulations to avoid abuses and excesses, but, mainly, the debate about the ethical aspects involved. This is because the technical possibilities of these resources not always are adequate or recommendable from the moral or ethical point of view.

When the technology involves software and machines equipped with artificial intelligence (AI), the definition of an efficient juridical norm, considering the need to harmonize domestic legal systems and international norms, is even more complex, especially in front of the multiple uses and unpredictability of conduct. AI-controlled equipment often starts to make decisions directly and autonomously.

In the ethical field, turned to the debate and the definition of moral limits to be observed collectively, which actions are tolerable and to what extent and direction machines operating with AI can be used? This subject is even more complex, given that “robots” are not capable of define which conduct is acceptable or not by themselves, acting only in logic of efficiency, destined to an especific end, that many times can not only oppose, but violate fundamental rights and established ethical concepts.

RESULTS

The ethical analysis is complex. When touching moral issues, clearly impose the definition not only of which essential values to be observed in determined societies, but the tolerable limits to the incorporation of new technologies and behaviors.

When it is about actions taken by non-humans, but by artificial intelligence machines, so capable of taking decisions autonomously, the debate becomes even more complex. Such equipment, generically called “robots”, are programmed not only to achieve an end precisely, but make their process more and more efficient, “learning” on the way and incorporating new forms of acting, not necessarily thought or imagined when it was originally programmed.

In Stuart Russel’s view, when thinking about ethical criteria to be applied to AI, the best would be to use a typical logic called Consequentialist Ethic, turned to judge the choices that shape the conducts based on their consequences. Still about the theme, Russel affirms that, in the absence of evidence of self-awareness of machines, it is not adequate to trust in its own moral evaluation, being more advisable to analyze the acting of the AI based on the results, on the effects effectively produced (01).

Such thought push away the possibility for the application of the utilitarian logic, which, as reminds Michael J. Sandel, “the most elevated objective of moral is to maximize happiness, ensuring the hegemony of pleasure over pain (02). Karl Popper, as reminds Russel, said since 1945 that was immoral to exchange one person’s pain to maximize the pleasure of another (03). In the same direction, affirms Kai-Fuu Lee and Chen Qiufan that an “explainable” AI is hard to be found, because it is built from data. Therefore, many times, an AI take incomprehensible decisions to humans in the name of a more efficient performance. Such fact, according to the authors, impose an essential ethic decision: whether it is advisable to give the machines decisions about conducts that might harm, cause pain or kill people. (04) The fact is that the increasingly constant use imposes an essential aspect which is the need to regulate the development since, from a technical point of view, there wouldn’t be no major limitations other than those linked to computational capacity. As Henry Kissinger, Eric Schmidt and Daniel Huttenlocher reminds, from the technical point of view the “borders” are violated easily, “which makes it difficult, but indispensable, the seek to mutual containment and surveillance”. 05)

CONCLUSIONS

The use of AI-technologies already is a reality. It's fundamental to discuss the effective ethical limits in its development and employment, that must be reflected in normative regulation. It is important to point out that the technical possibilities of the development of softwares and smart machines shouldn't mean a full authorization for the creation of any technology, regardless the consequences of its employment. That said, the collective reflection, involving the academy, governments, companies and researchers, must promote the seek for balance point between the incentive for development of new technologies and respect of ethical principles, essential to prevent that the machines end to impose their will and actions on humans.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Briefly, we suggest some measures on the subject:

1. To define ethical limits for the development of systems that operate models based on artificial intelligence;
2. To build a dialogue between the academy, governments, companies and researchers to the definition not only of which ethical principles must be observed, as well as which areas research must be directed;
3. To develop an international standard of use for the machines controlled by AI, widely accepted by the global players so that we can have a joint action to prevent technological abuses against human beings;
4. To think in means and resources so that it is possible to democratize the softwares in countries with different degrees of development, aiming to reduce the technological gap between countries;
5. To reinforce the human's role in controlling and programming technologies that involve AI, in order to prioritize the training of these individuals on plural and promoter contents.

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